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Restaurant Businesses in OECD Countries

Increased by an average of 18.14% between 2005 and 2022 in OECD countries

In 2022, the restaurant service sector in Europe and some other nations showed significant variance in the number of operational businesses. The data provide a detailed overview of the geographic distribution of restaurant businesses, highlighting differences between large and small countries as well as between mature and developing economies. Italy stands out at the top with 265,324 businesses operating in the restaurant sector. This figure reflects the importance of Italian cuisine and food culture not only for the national economy but also for international tourism. The widespread presence of restaurants, trattorias, and cafes throughout the peninsula is a distinctive feature of the country. Spain closely follows with 260,057 businesses. This high number can be attributed to Spain's strong culinary tradition and the popularity of tapas and Mediterranean cuisine, attracting both residents and tourists. The vibrancy of the restaurant sector in Spain is also fueled by the nightlife and the widespread habit of dining out. France, with 224,078 businesses, represents another major player in the European restaurant scene. The world-renowned French cuisine, with its refined techniques and wide variety of regional dishes, supports a vast number of restaurants and cafes. Additionally, gastronomic tourism is an important source of revenue for the country. Germany stands out with 186,619 businesses, reflecting a diversified culinary scene that goes beyond traditional beer gardens and German cuisine restaurants. The multiculturalism of German cities has led to a wide range of ethnic and international restaurants, contributing to a dynamic and growing sector. Greece, with 78,363 businesses, reflects its status as a major tourist destination where culinary experiences are an integral part of the journey. Similarly, Portugal, with 73,223 establishments, highlights its vibrant food culture and the importance of dining in social and tourist activities. In the Netherlands, 66,366 businesses indicate a robust food industry supported by both residents and a significant number of international tourists. Poland, with 57,695 establishments, shows the growing importance of dining out in Polish culture and the influence of Western eating habits. Belgium and Czechia, with 47,683 and 47,264 businesses respectively, demonstrate their strong positions in the European restaurant market. Belgium, known for its beer and chocolates, and Czechia, with its hearty traditional cuisine, both show significant numbers of restaurant activities. Austria (31,047), Hungary (27,839), and Sweden (25,741) reflect their medium-sized populations and strong cultural traditions related to dining. Israel, with 24,807 businesses, shows a vibrant culinary scene influenced by diverse cultural and religious traditions. Among the smaller countries, Bulgaria (18,933), Ireland (17,598), and Croatia (17,583) have notable numbers of businesses in the restaurant sector, reflecting growing tourism and a strong local dining culture. Serbia (17,072) and the Slovak Republic (16,042) also show significant numbers in the region. Switzerland, with 14,136 businesses, and Finland, with 12,882, demonstrate the presence of a strong restaurant sector despite their relatively small populations.

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Denmark (12,783) and Norway (9,861) reflect robust dining cultures in the Nordic region, supported by high standards of living. Bosnia and Herzegovina, with 9,240 businesses, and Costa Rica, with 8,776, show growing restaurant sectors in regions with developing economies. Slovenia (8,530) and Cyprus (5,582) indicate strongly tourism-driven food industries. The Baltic states of Lithuania (4,144), Estonia (2,894), and Latvia (2,888) show smaller but emerging restaurant sectors. Malta, with 2,731 businesses, reflects its role as a popular tourist destination with a rich culinary tradition. Finally, Luxembourg, with 2,401 businesses, represents a high concentration of dining establishments relative to its small population, driven by its affluent residents and a strong expatriate community. In summary, the data from 2022 reveal a dynamic and diverse restaurant sector across Europe and beyond. Countries with rich culinary traditions and strong tourism sectors tend to have higher numbers of restaurant businesses, reflecting the integral role of dining out in their cultural and economic life.

The Enterprises Engaged in Restaurant Activities in OECD Countries from 2005 to 2022. Between 2005 and 2022, the restaurant service sector exhibited diverse trends across various countries, with some nations experiencing significant growth in the number of enterprises and others facing contraction. Analyzing the data reveals various interesting trends and dynamics. Austria recorded a modest increase in the number of restaurant enterprises, with an absolute increase of 740 units, representing a percentage change of 2.44%. This suggests stability in the sector, with a slight increase that could be related to moderate economic growth or an increase in tourism. In Belgium, the number of enterprises increased by 19.35%, with 7,731 new activities. This notable increase could reflect a change in consumption habits, with a greater preference for dining out and a growing diversification of culinary offerings. Costa Rica saw an impressive increase of 87.80%, rising from 4,673 to 8,776 enterprises. This growth could be attributed to the expansion of the tourism sector and a growing popularity of the country as a travel destination, which fueled the demand for restaurant services. The Czech Republic registered a decrease of 4.59%, with a loss of 2,273 enterprises. This decline might be related to economic, demographic, or structural changes that negatively affected the sector. Denmark saw an increase of 5.85%, with an increment of 706 enterprises. Again, this moderate growth could reflect a solid economy and an expanding restaurant market. Estonia showed the highest percentage growth, with an increase of 156.79%, adding 1,767 new enterprises. This extraordinary increase could be due to rapid economic development and modernization of the service sector. Finland recorded an increase of 42.20%, with 3,823 new enterprises. This suggests strong sector growth, likely supported by increased disposable income and a greater interest in gastronomy. France, with an increase of 23.48% and 42,607 new enterprises, continues to consolidate its position as a leader in the restaurant sector, benefiting from a strong culinary culture and flourishing tourism. Germany registered a notable increase of 54.85%, with 66,105 new enterprises. This reflects robust economic growth and a diversification of the culinary offer that has attracted both residents and tourists. Greece saw a slight decrease of 1.63%, with 1,297 fewer enterprises. This decline might be the result of economic difficulties or a reduction in domestic demand. Hungary registered a decrease of 5.87%, with 1,737 fewer enterprises. This could reflect economic challenges or changes in consumer preferences. Ireland showed significant growth of 80.71%, with 7,860 new enterprises. This increase could be correlated with robust economic recovery and a boom in the tourism sector. Italy, with an increase of 13.70% and 31,970 new enterprises, confirms its strong culinary tradition and a growing restaurant sector, supported by constant tourism and strong domestic demand. Latvia recorded an increase of 28.47%, with 640 new enterprises, while Lithuania saw growth of 52.75%, with 1,431 new enterprises. These increases reflect an expansion of the service sector in these Baltic countries. Luxembourg had a modest increase of 2.56%, with 60 new enterprises, suggesting stability in the sector. The Netherlands showed an impressive increase of 110.35%, with 34,815 new

enterprises. This strong growth could be attributed to a combination of economic growth, increased tourism, and cultural changes towards more frequent dining out. Norway registered an increase of 32.70%, with 2,430 new enterprises, reflecting stable economic growth and a thriving restaurant market. Poland saw an increase of 27.10%, with 12,302 new enterprises, indicating an expanding sector, probably supported by a growing middle class and increased urbanization. Portugal experienced a decrease of 9.85%, with 7,999 fewer enterprises. This decline might result from economic difficulties or a contraction of the domestic market. Slovakia recorded the highest percentage increase, with an incredible 1581.55%, rising from 954 to 16,042 enterprises. This extraordinary growth might be due to significant economic reforms and a boom in the service sector. Slovenia saw growth of 42.29%, with 2,535 new enterprises, reflecting an expansion of the restaurant sector. Spain registered a slight decrease of 0.74%, with 1,940 fewer enterprises, suggesting overall stability in the sector despite slight fluctuations. Sweden saw an increase of 23.66%, with 4,925 new enterprises, indicating strong sector growth. Bulgaria experienced a decrease of 9.55%, with 1,999 fewer enterprises, likely due to economic difficulties. Cyprus saw a slight decrease of 4.79%, with 281 fewer enterprises. Romania showed significant growth of 77.82%, with 12,959 new enterprises, reflecting rapid expansion of the restaurant service sector. In conclusion, the data shows a diverse range of trends in the restaurant sector in Europe and other nations between 2005 and 2022, with some countries experiencing robust growth and others facing contractions. The differences can be attributed to various factors, including economic, demographic, and cultural changes.

Conclusions. The enterprises engaged in restaurant service activities grew by an average of 18.14% between 2005 and 2022 in OECD countries. The countries where the value of enterprises in the restaurant service sector grew the most between 2005 and 2022 are Slovakia with 1581.55%, Estonia with 156.79%, and the Netherlands with 110.35%. However, there are also countries where this value decreased, namely Hungary with -5.87%, Bulgaria with -9.55%, and Portugal with -9.85%. Considering 2022, with the number of enterprises operating in the restaurant service sector set at 100, it emerges that 16.23% are present in Italy, 15.91% in Spain, 13.71% in France, and 11.41% in Germany. Italy leads the ranking of OECD countries for the number of enterprises operating in the restaurant service sector, with a total of 265,324 enterprises in 2022.

Declarations

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References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

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